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IMPROVING INDEPENDENT ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING BASED ON A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH

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Abstract: This article analyzes the theoretical foundations and practical mechanisms of the competency-based approach in effectively organizing the process of independent learning of the English language. Through the competency-based approach, ways are shown to form an active, responsible and creative attitude towards the language learning process in students. The article substantiates the role of motivation, metacognitive strategies, self-control and the use of digital technologies in organizing independent learning. It also highlights methods that serve to develop communicative, cultural and information and communication competencies in mastering the English language. The results of the study are enriched with proposals aimed at introducing modern methodological approaches in the process of teaching the English language.

Keywords: Competency-based approach, independent learning, English language learning, language competence, mastery strategies, metacognitive approach, communicative competence.

Introduction.

In an era of increasing importance of the English language in the context of global communication, science, technology and international cooperation, its effective mastery has become one of the pressing issues of the education system. Especially today, when the need for independent learning is growing, it is extremely important to form internal motivation in students to learn a foreign language, ensure their personal growth and develop language competencies. The competency-based approach is considered the main methodological principle in achieving such goals.

The competency-based approach is an approach aimed at the application of knowledge, skills and competencies in life situations, the readiness of a person for practical activity and the ability to independently form their own knowledge. This approach focuses the educational process not only on imparting knowledge, but also on the formation of the student as a person, on the development of such life skills as problem solving, communication, planning and analysis of their activities. In independent learning of English, it is this approach that increases the student's activity in learning the language, encourages him to work on himself and involves him in the process of self-development.

In today's digital age, there are many opportunities for independent mastery of the English language: online courses, mobile applications, virtual learning platforms, artificial intelligence tools and other modern technologies help students freely master a foreign language. However, the effective use of these opportunities requires the student to be self-aware, ambitious and responsible. In such conditions, the competency-based approach serves as the most appropriate methodological basis for forming an independent learning process in accordance with the student's personal needs, learning styles and goals. This article discusses ways to improve the process of

independent mastery of the English language based on the competency-based approach, the theoretical and practical aspects of this approach, and the language competencies that need to be formed in the personality of a modern student. Recommendations are also made on the creation of pedagogical technologies, methods and environments that support independent learning.

Methodology:

In the modern educational process, a sound scientific and methodological approach is necessary for the effective organization, management and improvement of independent learning of the English language, and the competency-based methodology is at the heart of such an approach. This methodology focuses not only on assessing the student's knowledge, but also on how he can apply his knowledge and skills in real-life situations. Therefore, the proposals developed on the basis of scientific research, observations, comparisons and experience put forward in the article are based on the didactic principles of the competency-based approach.

The theoretical foundations of the methodology were analyzed by the views of advanced foreign and domestic pedagogical scientists, in particular, the theories of person-centered education, activity-based approach and metacognitive learning. Through these approaches, the activity, motivation, critical thinking and self-control skills of an independent learner are developed. In particular, the formation of communicative, linguistic, sociocultural and information-communication competencies in the process of learning English was taken into account in the methodological approach as an important factor.

The main methods used in the article are as follows:

Analytical-methodological approach - previously published scientific articles, textbooks, teaching aids were analyzed and how the competency-based approach was expressed in them was studied. Through this, existing methodological shortcomings and areas for improvement were identified.

Experimental-pedagogical method - interactive exercises, tasks, reflection methods, self-assessment techniques that stimulate independent learning in the process of teaching English were introduced and their effectiveness was evaluated. During these experiments, group learning, feedback, and metacognitive monitoring methods were used in working with students.

Questionnaire and interview method - surveys were conducted among language learners and English teachers to study their attitude to independent learning based on a competency-based approach. The results revealed the difficulties and needs that students face in working on themselves.

Diagnostic analysis - assessments were conducted based on tests and diagnostic questions to measure students' independent learning skills, and the level of student independent activity was determined. Based on this information, proposals were developed to adjust the curriculum.

The article also presents the experience of working with a specific group on an experimental basis, in which the results of studying the traditional approach and the competency-based approach were compared. This served to strengthen the theoretical foundations of the methodology in a practical way. In general, the methodological foundations of this article are aimed at enriching modern English language education

with an approach based on the active participation of the student, encouraging independent learning and serving the development of real competencies. This will serve not only as a basis for learning English, but also for its free use in everyday, professional and scientific activities.

Literature and source analysis:

A deep understanding of the theoretical and practical foundations of the competency-based approach in independent English language learning requires, first of all, a deep study of advanced literature and sources in this area. In the process of writing this article, popular and scientific and methodological sources on the issues of educational methodology, foreign language teaching, organization of independent learning, competency-based approach, as well as teaching based on digital technologies were analyzed.

First of all, theoretical views on the competency-based approach are deeply covered in the pedagogical works of such Russian scientists as V.V. Serikov, A.V. Khutorskoy, I.A. Zimnyaya, E.F. Zeer. In particular, A.V. Khutorskoy's theory of the formation of competencies, his approach to the integration of personal and metasubject competencies in the educational process formed the ideological basis of this article. I.A. Zimnyaya's broad interpretation of the concept of "competence" made it possible to analyze the foundations of person-centered education and activity-based learning.

In the analysis of foreign literature, the studies of such researchers as J. Brown, D. Little, L. Bachman, H. Holec on independent language learning, self-control, metacognitive approach and the development of language competencies were an important source. In particular, Henry Holec's developments on "learner autonomy" served to illuminate the psychological and methodological foundations of independent learning.

The work of local researchers - Sh.S. Sharipov, M.A. Jo'rayev, O. Khasanboeva, D. Otamurotov on the methodology of teaching a foreign language, the use of modern educational technologies, and the organization of lessons based on interactive methods helped to identify the prospects for introducing a competency-based approach in the conditions of the Uzbek education system.

Also, the decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at improving the quality of education, accelerating the study and teaching of foreign languages, in particular, Resolution No. PQ-5117 (May 19, 2021) and Resolution No. PQ-2909 (April 6, 2017), were analyzed, justifying the fact that the transition to a competency-based approach to teaching English is an important direction of state policy. In addition, the levels of language competencies, their assessment criteria, and guidelines for independent mastery proposed by various international organizations (UNESCO, CEFR - Common European Framework of Reference for Languages) were also studied through comparative analysis. In particular, the "learner-centered" approach in the CEFR system, the criteria of independence, communicativeness, and cultural adaptability in language acquisition enriched the theoretical foundations of the article. The analyzed literature and sources served as an important basis for the scientific and theoretical substantiation of the competency-based approach to independent learning of the English language, the development of practical mechanisms, and the identification of existing shortcomings

and needs. This made it possible to adapt the recommendations presented in the article to the real educational environment.

Discussion:

Currently, the focus of the educational process is on the student's personal activity, independent thinking, and internal need for self-development. Methodological approaches that stimulate these needs are especially important in the process of mastering foreign languages, in particular, English. From this point of view, the competency-based approach stands out as one of the most effective directions for organizing independent learning. Based on the scientific research, observations, and experiments conducted in this article, the existing problems in independent learning of the English language and ways to solve them were thoroughly analyzed.

The study found that most students are limited to the knowledge gained in the classroom when mastering a foreign language, and do not have sufficient knowledge of independent learning strategies, self-assessment methods, and metacognitive approaches. This situation leads to a slowdown in the development of their language competencies. At the same time, although some students use various online platforms, mobile applications, or independent course materials, there is a need for methodological guidance on important aspects such as how to effectively use these resources, creating a personal learning plan, and self-control. On this basis, learning English through a competency-based approach provides not only the acquisition of knowledge, but also preparation for its application in real-life situations. A language learner can independently form competencies such as self-analysis, identifying mistakes, adapting to communication, and understanding the cultural context. This shows that the competency-based approach is effective not only didactically, but also psychologically, socially, and culturally.

Based on the experiment conducted in the article, in the experimental group using the competency-based approach, significant positive changes were observed in the interest in independent learning, the quality of language acquisition, speech activity, and self-assessment skills. These results confirm that, unlike the traditional approach, it is possible to achieve high efficiency by increasing the student's activity, taking into account his individual capabilities, and adapting education to the individual. Also, through the independent education model based on the competency-based approach, the role of the teacher also changes radically - he is no longer a knowledge provider, but a guide, advisor, and motivator. This strengthens the principles of mutual respect, dialogue, and cooperation in the pedagogical process.

However, it should also be recognized that for the full implementation of this approach, certain infrastructure and methodological conditions are necessary: modern learning resources, e-learning platforms, tasks that encourage student independence, and professional development programs for teachers themselves are important factors. The competency-based approach to independent English language learning is a person-oriented, activity-based and real-life approach that forms not only language competencies, but also personal and social activity. By applying this approach in practice, it is possible to form a competent person who meets modern requirements, thinks independently, and can work on himself.

Conclusion.

Independent English language learning is today an integral part not only of the educational process, but also of the personal and professional development of each individual. The gradual transition to a competency-based approach in the education system of Uzbekistan has created the need to organize this process in a more effective, person-oriented and activity-based way. Based on the scientific and theoretical analysis, practical observations and experience conducted in this article, the following conclusions were drawn:

A competency-based approach is an approach that focuses not only on providing knowledge, but also on the student's readiness for practical activity, independent thinking, and ability to solve problem situations, which ensures high efficiency in mastering the English language.

In the formation of independent English learning skills, the student's motivation, ability to self-assess, and the level of use of metacognitive strategies are decisive factors. These aspects are actively developed precisely through the competency-based approach.

Experimental studies have shown that students who were taught based on the competency-based approach were more inclined to work independently and achieved high results in the process of language acquisition. This changed their attitude towards the learning process in a positive direction and strengthened their confidence in independent learning.

When modern information and communication technologies, interactive methods, differentiated approaches, and feedback are introduced into the educational process, the effectiveness of the independent learning process increases, and the role of the teacher should be more guiding and motivating.

An integrated approach to independent learning of English is necessary: it should simultaneously develop language competence, communicative skills, cultural understanding, and digital literacy.

On this basis, the following practical recommendations are put forward:

It is necessary to introduce independent learning models based on a competency-based approach in teaching English in higher and secondary specialized educational institutions.

Individual curricula, self-assessment tools, diagnostic tests, and digital learning platforms should be widely used to form independent learning competencies in students.

Teachers themselves should also regularly undergo advanced training courses on a competency-based approach and thoroughly master modern methodological approaches.

Resources for independent learning (electronic textbooks, video lectures, exercise banks) should be created based on national content and meet the socio-cultural needs of students in language learning.

In short, organizing the process of independent learning of the English language based on a competence approach is a priority of modern education, which serves to prepare students for life activities, to educate them as competitive and globally thinking individuals.

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